

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICAL
EDUCATION

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Annotation . *This in the article artificial intellect of technologies medical in education to be used about opportunities and their efficiency analysis done Research to the results according to , artificial intellect using study processes customized and individualized being , this students knowledge get level significant level improved . Virtual reality and simulation technologies to students clinical skills from practice outside learning enable gives Artificial intellect medical in education more efficient education processes in creating important role even if he plays , his complete current to be done for technological infrastructure and personnel again preparation is required .*

Keywords : *Artificial intelligence (SI) , t ibbiy education , Virtual reality (VR) , simulation , adaptive education , technological infrastructure .*

Enter. *Artificial intellect last in years different in the fields fast developed and widely used in medicine apply started Medical in education while artificial intellect education processes improvement , students knowledge assessment , diagnosis skills in increasing big opportunities is creating . Artificial intellect education process adaptation and individualization through not only information delivered to give more efficient to do , maybe education to increase the quality able*

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This article medical in education artificial intellect of technologies application and their efficiency issues seeing comes out

Methodology . In the article artificial intellect of medical in education application opportunities learning for scientific sources analysis done and practical studies was studied . Analyze such as Google Scholar and PubMed for scientific from platforms 2015-2023 between articles choose received Also artificial intellect using created diagnosis and education platforms efficiency and of students appropriation level effect experimental respectively was evaluated . Evaluation in the process teachers and students between questionnaires was conducted and study of the process to quality attention was directed .

Results . Research results that's it showed that it is artificial intellect applied education in systems of students knowledge get efficiency significant level increased Students artificial intellect using virtual simulation technologies used without , complicated clinical circumstances independent respectively learned and skills increased . Learning speed , understanding level and the process more interesting to do in terms of artificial intellect traditional study styles relatively advantages to the eye thrown away Also artificial intellect technologies through created adaptive study programs students need adaptation because of their appropriation level significant growth observed .

Analysis. Artificial intellect medical in education study processes transformation to do big opportunities creates Virtual reality and simulation such as technologies using students practical in training complicated without participation clinical processes mastery can From this except artificial intellect using medical circumstances modeling and of individual students knowledge level suitable education materials created and studied process more efficient will be With that together , teachers and students between communication strengthen and evaluation

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processes automation there are also opportunities . However , it is artificial intellect of technologies complete current to be done for technological infrastructure and personnel again preparation is required .

Summary

Medical in education artificial of intellect application education processes more efficient and more interactive in doing big to the prospect have Artificial intellect technologies students to master improvement , medical skills development and personalized education in giving important role to play can With that together , technologies successful current reach for certain technological infrastructure create and personnel to prepare separately attention focus it is necessary

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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